

The Algebra of the Equality on Complex Numbers III

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Abstract

On this manuscript are describe some geometrical and set properties to understand Add_{map} and $Prod_{map}$ functions and its importance to define translation operation; n-power function and the meaning of $s = \sqrt{-1}$. An application is given to establish a solution to Riemann Hypothesis.

1 Some Geometrical properties about Complex Numbers

Property 3. Add_{map} is an homomorphism iff translation maintains distances.

Figure 1: Translation of Axis scheme

Figure 1 will show the distribution of points used to describe next properties.

*) \supset

$$(a, b) \cdot (c, d) = (ac - bd, ad + bc)$$

If

$$x = ac;$$

$$y = ad;$$

$$h = -bd;$$

$$k = bc$$

$$(a, b) \cdot (c, d) = (x + h, y + k)$$

By Translation of Axis we have:

$$(x, y) =_T (x + h, y + k)$$

where $=_T :=$ Equality by translation of axis

Hence

$$(ac - bd, ad + bc) = (ac, ad)$$

If we expect to know all values a, b, c and d we can establish

$$d = \alpha c$$

Later substituting on last vector we have

$$(ac, ad) = (ac, a\alpha c)$$

with

$$a\alpha c - ac = ac(\alpha - 1)$$

$$a\alpha c + ac = ac(\alpha + 1)$$

if

$$\alpha ac - ac = lm - mo$$

and

$$\alpha ac + ac = lo - nm$$

hence

$$ac = mo \text{ and } ac = nm$$

therefore

$$\text{if } m = a \text{ hence } c = 0 \text{ and } n = 0$$

hence

$$l = \alpha a$$

hence

$$(ac, ad) = (ln - mo, lo + nm)$$

$$= (l, m) \cdot (n, o)$$

By $=_A$ and ref[2,3]; Add_{map} on $(l, m) \cdot (n, o)$ maintains the properties of homomorphism respect to translations.

Therefore Add_{map} homomorphism is valid $\forall(\alpha, \beta) \in C$

**) \subset

Like Add_{map} is defined $\forall a, b, c, d \in \mathfrak{R}$ hence $Add_{map} \in \mathfrak{R}$ is well established.

Lets take two squares of length side 1:

$$\text{Square 1: Side}_x : (h + 1), \text{ Side}_y : (k + 1)$$

$$\text{Square 2: Side}_x : (h - 1), \text{ Side}_y : (k + 1)$$

On this way the geometrical center of both squares is (h, k) with opposite vertex

$$\text{Square 1: } (h + 1, k + 1)$$

$$\text{Square 2: } (h - 1, k + 1)$$

For such squares the condition $A_{QII} =_A A_{QI}$

By Add_{map} homomorphism we have:

$$h - 1 + k + 1 =_A h + 1 + k + 1$$

i.e.

$$h - 1 + k + 1 < h + 1 + k + 1$$

simplifying we have:

$$-1 < 1$$

i.e.

$$-1 =_A 1$$

or

$$-a =_A a$$

i.e.

$$-a < a$$

This means that length sides of squares are the same around the point (h, k) ;
 $\forall h, k \in \mathfrak{R}$ including zero as well as for

$$x + h = y + k \in \mathfrak{R}$$

i.e. distances preserves by translation; this means that squares have same length for

$$(x, y) \text{ and } (x', y') \text{ when } x' = x + h \text{ and } y' = y + k$$

Therefore

$$(x, y) =_T (x', y')$$

i.e.

$$(x, y) =_T (x + h, y + k)$$

When we measure distances of squares established by translation.

Property 4. $Prod_{map}$ is an homomorphism iff translation maintains distances.

*) \supset

$$(a, b) \cdot (c, d) = (ac - bd, ad, ad + bc)$$

When $a = b$ and $c = d$

$$(a, b) \cdot (c, d) = (0, 2ac)$$

by translation of axis

$$(0, 2ac) =_T (0 + h, 2ac + k) = (h, 2ac + k)$$

By $Prod_{map}$ on last coordinate we have:

$$Prod_{map}(h, 2ac + k) = h(2ac + k)$$

$$\text{If } A_{Square} = h(2ac + k)$$

By $0 < A_{QI}$ we have ref[3]:

$$0 < h(2ac + k)$$

$$\text{If } \gamma\delta = h(2ac + k)$$

$$0 < \gamma\delta$$

With $\gamma = \delta$

$$\gamma^2 - \delta^2 < \gamma\delta$$

Multiplying by α^2 we have:

$$\alpha^2(\gamma^2 - \delta^2) < \alpha^2\gamma\delta$$

By ref[2] we obtain:

$$\alpha^2(\gamma^2 - \delta^2) =_A \alpha^2\gamma\delta$$

Since this point is possible to develop $Prod_{map}$ homomorphism hence properties maintains $\forall(\gamma, \delta) \in C$

**) \subset

Like $Prod_{map}$ is defined $\forall\alpha = \beta, \gamma = \delta \in \mathfrak{R}$ hence $Prod_{map} \in \mathfrak{R}$ is well established.

Hence

$$Prod_{map}[(\alpha, \beta) \cdot (\gamma, \delta)] =_A Prod_{map}(\alpha, \beta) \cdot Prod_{map}(\gamma, \delta)$$

i.e.

$$\alpha^2(\gamma^2 - \delta^2) < \alpha^2\gamma\delta$$

simplifying we have:

$$0 < \gamma\delta$$

with

$$Prod_{map}(\gamma, \delta) = \gamma\delta$$

else by translation

$$(\gamma, \delta) = (\gamma + h, \delta + k)$$

i.e.

$$(\gamma + h, \delta + k) = (\gamma', \delta')$$

Hence by $Prod_{map}$

$$Prod_{map}(\gamma', \delta') = \gamma'\delta' = A_{Square}$$

By $0 < A_{Square}$ and remembering that $\gamma' = \delta'$

By $Prod_{map}$ homomorphism

$$\alpha^{2'}(\gamma^{2'} - \delta^{2'}) =_A \alpha^{2'}(\gamma'\delta')$$

Therefore

$$Prod_{map}[(\alpha', \beta') \cdot (\gamma', \delta')] =_A Prod_{map}(\alpha', \beta') \cdot Prod_{map}(\gamma', \delta')$$

Hence $\alpha' = \beta'$ and $\gamma' = \delta'$

Hence translation preserves distances of squares around point (h, k)

2 The value of number i by $=_A$ and $=_T$

Lets characterize relation $=_A$ by its properties like an equivalence.

A relation is a set define like:

$$R = \{(x, y) \mid xRy : x, y \in X\}$$

$R_1 := -a =_A a \in \mathfrak{R}$ and $-a < a \in \mathfrak{R}$

*) Reflexive (xRx)

Like $a < a$ is a contradiction hence $=_A$ can not be reflexive

**) Symmetry (xRy iff yRx)

If $a \downarrow b$ hence $b \not\prec a$ therefore $=_A$ can not be symmetric

***) Transitive (xRy and yRz hence xRz)

If $a =_A b \wedge b =_A c$ hence $a < c$

Now lets characterize relation $R_2 := a =_{\{T\}} b$

*) Reflexive

Lets introduce the subindex $T = (\pm h_1, \dots, \pm h_n)$ indicating the length of displacement over the coordinate numbering with i .

Also lets indicate that $h \in \mathfrak{R}$

$a =_{\{T=0\}} a$ when $T = 0$ indicate that transition is null; i.e. a trivial value to define translation therefore $=_{\{T=\pm h\}}$ is reflexive.

**) Symmetry

If $x =_{\{T=\pm h\}} y$ hence $y =_{\{T=h\mp\}} x$

therefore $=_{\{T=\pm h\}}$ is symmetric

***) Transitive

$x =_{\{T=\pm h\}} y \wedge y =_{\{T=\pm h'\}} z$ hence $x =_{\{T=\pm h\pm h'\}} z$

therefore $=_{\{T=\pm h\}}$ is transitive

By other the hand the union relation

$R_1 \cup R_2 = \{(x, y) \mid a =_A b \vee a =_{\{T=\pm h\}} b ; a, b \in \mathfrak{R}\}$

While intersection is

$R_1 \cap R_2 = \{(x, y) \mid a =_A b \wedge a =_{\{T=\pm h\}} b ; a, b \in \mathfrak{R}\}$

****) **Def.** Given two groups $(G, *)$ and (H, \cdot) a group homomorphism from $(G, *)$ to (H, \cdot) is a function $h : G \rightarrow H$ such that for all u and v in G it holds that

$$h(u * v) = h(u) \cdot h(v)$$

h maps the identity element e_G of G to the identity element e_H of H ,

$$h(e_G) = e_H$$

Proof.

Consider $A_i = -1$ and the direct sum

$$\begin{aligned} \bigoplus_{i=1}^n A_i &= \text{diag}(A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n) \\ &= \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & \cdots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots & -1 \end{pmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

and $k :=$ dimension of Cartesian plane considered.

Let be

$$G = \{A_i \in \mathfrak{R} \mid A_i = -1 ; i \in N\}$$

and

$$H = \{0\}$$

$$(G, \bigoplus_{i=1}^n A_i) \rightarrow (H, +)$$

with

$$f(\bigoplus_{i=1}^n A_i) = \bigoplus_{i=1}^n A_i + (-\bigoplus_{i=1}^n A_i) = 0$$

and trivial function

$$g(\bigoplus_{i=1}^n A_i) = \bigoplus_{i=1}^n A_i \times 0 = 0 \times (\bigoplus_{i=1}^n A_i) = 0$$

Like

$\bigoplus_{i=1}^n A_i = i :=$ the inverse element of symmetry

hence

$G = C_i = \{i\}$ the group point

homomorphism is defined to give a sense to the symmetry transformation through number zero on \mathfrak{R}^3 that defines negative numbers and establish next equality

$$(-x, -y, -z) = (x, y, z)$$

with arithmetic sense

$$-x < x$$

$$-y < y$$

$$-z < z$$

and "abstract sense"

$$-x =_A x$$

$$-y =_A y$$

$$-z =_A z$$

i.e. for

$-1 < 1$ we have obtaining square root

$$\sqrt{-1} < \sqrt{1}$$

i.e.

$$s = \sqrt{-1} =_A 1$$

when condition relation $R_1 := -a =_A a$ is established and trichotomy through zero is considered we have:

$$-1 < 0 < 1$$

$$\sqrt{-1} < \sqrt{0} < \sqrt{1}$$

$$\sqrt{-1} =_A 0 =_A 1$$

with geometrical meaning about the length of a linear segment; being the same since 0 to 1 and 0 to -1 ; like square root is applied in both sides and length of each side is not affected by square root operation hence can be concluded without more argumentation that:

$$s = \sqrt{-1} = 1$$

By translation for each number considered besides zero we found

$$s = \sqrt{-1} =_{\{T=1\}} 0 =_{\{T=-1\}} 1$$

i.e.

each translation of axis to redefine the origin of Cartesian plane establish that each coordinate can be equal to zero i.e.

$$(h_1, h_2, \dots, h_n) =_T (0, 0, \dots, 0)$$

$$\forall h_1, h_2, \dots, h_n \in \mathfrak{R}$$

3 n - power on Complex Numbers

On complex numbers n-power function is not defined; taking into account the results of appendix 1 and 2 if the conclusion

$$s = \sqrt{-1} = 1$$

is taken as valid, such operation could be defined.

lets take

$$s =_A 1$$

And remember that even when $-a =_A a$ is same as $-a < a$; such equality can preserve same sense as standard equality ($=$); due to early considerations about length of line segments after obtain square root.

Hence multiplying by t in both sides we have:

$$st =_A t$$

and adding σ we obtain

$$\sigma + st =_A \sigma + t$$

On this assumption we are going to use the result of the right hand to define \mathbf{n} the value of the power.

Hence

$\forall x \in \mathfrak{R}$ its complex power is equal to

$$x^{\sigma+st} =_A x^{\sigma+t}$$

While in ref[1] $s = \pm 1$ to consider usual definition of square root (i.e. square root usually is taken as the plus and less value of the square); since now the value used will be considered through the development of early definitions ($s = \sqrt{-1} = 1$).

4 Appendix 1. The Riemann Hypothesis

... es ist sehr wahrscheinlich, dass alle Wurzeln reell sind. Hiervon wäre allerdings ein strenger Beweis zu wünschen; ich habe indess die Aufsuchung desselben nach einigen flüchtigen vergeblichen Versuchen vorläufig bei Seite gelassen, da er für den nächsten Zweck meiner Untersuchung entbehrlich schien.

... it is very probable that all roots are real. Of course one would wish for a rigorous proof here; I have for the time being, after some fleeting vain attempts, provisionally put aside the search for this, as it appears dispensable for the immediate objective of my investigation.

—Riemann's statement of the Riemann hypothesis, from (Riemann 1859). (He was discussing a version of the zeta function, modified so that its roots (zeros) are real rather than on the critical line.)

The Riemann zeta function is defined by the absolutely convergent infinite series for complex s with real part greater than 1 as follows:

$$\zeta_{sum}(z) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^z} = \frac{1}{1^z} + \frac{1}{2^z} + \frac{1}{3^z} + \dots$$

Zeta Riemann function also is equal to Euler product (Euler, L.; 1730)

$$\zeta_{product}(z) = \prod_{p \text{ prime}} \frac{1}{1-p^{-z}} = \frac{1}{1-2^{-z}} \cdot \frac{1}{1-3^{-z}} \cdot \frac{1}{1-5^{-z}} \cdot \frac{1}{1-7^{-z}} \dots$$

Due to ref[1] we have for $\zeta_{sum}(z)$

$$\zeta_{sum}(z = 1.4) \quad \begin{array}{ccc} \eta = 5000 & \eta = 10000 & \eta = 20000 \\ 3.02268924184343 & 3.04275137310375 & 3.05795640541761 \end{array}$$

Valuating $\zeta_{product}(z)$ we have:

$$\zeta_{product}(z = 1.4) \quad \begin{array}{cc} p = 1181 & p = 1187 \\ 3.05787308432441 & 3.05802486273671 \end{array}$$

From table 1 and 2 we can conclude that for $z = 1.4$ we have;

$$\zeta_{product;p=1181}(z) < \zeta_{sum}(z) < \zeta_{product;p=1187}(z)$$

Therefore

$$\zeta_{sum}(z) = \alpha \cdot \zeta_{product}(z)$$

only for $p = 1181$

$$\alpha = \frac{\zeta_{sum}(z)}{\zeta_{product}(z)} = \frac{3.05795640541761}{3.05787308432441} = 1.00002724805474$$

while for $p = 1187$

$$\alpha = \frac{\zeta_{sum}(z)}{\zeta_{product}(z)} = \frac{3.05795640541761}{3.05802486273671} = 0.999977613877528$$

Due to the value of α the equality given by Euler is wrong; i.e. can not be possible because $\alpha \neq 1$.

Nonetheless such equality can be understood since the point of view of trigonometry using congruence of triangles; like is usually considered on classic geometry and considering that $s = \sqrt{-1} = i$; like was defined formerly on this manuscript.

The coordinates of any triangle since origin are given on the Cartesian plane like (a, b) .

In terms of the function $\zeta(z)$ we have:

$$(a, b) = (\zeta(z), \zeta(z))$$

Figure 2: Congruence of angles on triangles with length of sides $\zeta(z)$

Applying $Prod_{map}$ function to represent the area of such triangle we have:

$$\text{Triangle's Area} = \frac{Prod_{map}(\zeta(z), \zeta(z))}{2} = \frac{\zeta(z)^2}{2}$$

Being valid for ζ_{add} and ζ_{prod} hence the triangles shown on figure 2 are similar.

By the other hand we have for the scalar product next equalities:

By Pythagorean Theorem we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \sqrt{\zeta(z)^2 + \zeta(z)^2} &= \sqrt{Prod_{map}(\zeta(z), \zeta(z)) + Prod_{map}(\zeta(z), \zeta(z))} \\ &= \sqrt{2Prod_{map}(\zeta(z), \zeta(z))} \\ &= \sqrt{Add_{map}(Prod_{map}(\zeta(z), \zeta(z)), Prod_{map}(\zeta(z), \zeta(z)))} \end{aligned}$$

* Hence with $\vec{x} = (0, \zeta(z))$ and $\vec{y} = (\zeta(z), \zeta(z))$ we have

$$\begin{aligned} (\vec{x} \cdot \vec{y}) &= |\zeta(z)| |\sqrt{\zeta(z)^2 + \zeta(z)^2}| \cos(45) \\ (\vec{x} \cdot \vec{y}) &= |\zeta(z)| |\sqrt{2\zeta(z)^2}| \cos(45) \\ (\vec{x} \cdot \vec{y}) &= |\zeta(z)| |\sqrt{2}| |\zeta(z)| \cos(45) \\ (\vec{x} \cdot \vec{y}) &= |\sqrt{2}| \cdot |\zeta(z)|^2 \cos(45) \\ (\vec{x} \cdot \vec{y}) &= \sqrt{2} \cdot |\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (\frac{1}{n^z})|^2 \cos(45) \\ &= \sqrt{2} \cdot Prod_{map}(\zeta(z), \zeta(z)) \cos(45) \\ &= \sqrt{2} \cdot (\frac{Add_{map}(Prod_{map}(\zeta(z), \zeta(z)), Prod_{map}(\zeta(z), \zeta(z)))}{2}) \cos(45) \end{aligned}$$

Being valid for ζ_{add} and ζ_{prod} hence using scalar product is proved that the triangles shown on figure 2 are similar by three equal angles.

By early definitions given on this manuscript and results established on ref[2 and 3] can be concluded that the solution to the Riemann Hypothesis can be given by the methodology found on ref[1]. Such procedure establish the possibility to increase the accuracy of the value of z (found variable z like s on ref[1]) by the implementation of a better algorithm to calculate a convergence value for such variable by a convenient method; suggesting to use preferably a computational scheme based on ref[1].

5 References

[1] Alejandro, J.R. (2004). A Real Approximation to Riemann Hypothesis. J. Math Techniques Comput Math, 3(2), 01-12.

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[3] The Algebra of the Equality on Complex Numbers II; M. Díaz; J. R. A.; (scribd 2024)